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Research Article

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF URETEROSCOPY WITHOUT FLUOROSCOPY FOR URETERAL AND RENAL STONES

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Abstract:

Objective:

We aim to study the effect of using ureteroscopy without fluoroscopy in children with ureteric and renal stones.

Study Design: Experimental study

Place and Duration of Study: Sindh Government Lyari General Hospital, Karachi from January 2015 till Dec 2018

Methodology:

This study was carried out on every patients diagnosed with renal and ureteral stones in department of Urology. We included all patients with stone size less than 2 cm. Ureteroscopy was performed without fluoroscopy. We obtained the demographics, clinical history and stone size details from the medical record database. However post-operative results and complication details were collected with follow-up and information was analyzed using SPSS Version 20.

Results

In our data calculi was found in 44 Male (59% of total Patients) and 30 Females (41% of total patients) where the Mean age and standard deviation was 15.29 ± 6.86 . Resulting Complications without fluoroscopy were 12%. Overall 93% Patients were stone free while CIRF was 7% without fluoroscopic operation.

Conclusion

This confirms that the exposure from radiation has harmful effects and that even without the use of fluoroscopy, ureteroscopy can be performed successfully and stones can be removed.

Key words: Ureteroscopy, without fluoroscopy, ureteral and renal stones.

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INTRODUCTION:

Kidney stones can develop along the urinary tract anywhere from ureters to kidney. These stones are formed due to the higher concentration of salt and minerals in the urine. Usually these stones precipitate out in urine however some need surgical treatment or ultrasound or other similar techniques for flushing out with the urine.

In case of larger stones, surgeries or other treatments are suggested by the physician. The maximum number of stones found are made of Calcium, Struvite, Cystin and Uric acid.

Most kidney stones pass and don't necessarily need treatment however in case of stone sizes greater than 2 cm, treatment become necessary and one of the most prevalent methods involve the use of fluoroscopy however as people are getting more and more aware with the harmful effects of radiation hazards linked with the medical imaging, the need for newer and better methods has become significant. [1,2] Although every method has its merits and related demerits yet choosing the ideal alternative is quite challenging.

According to the USA Food and Drug Administration, physicians are suggested to lessen their exposure to radiations caused by fluoroscopic procedures. [3]

Stone diseases have been stated to rise up to 77% in asymptomatic intracranial stones and around 26% of them will need to undergo surgery. [4,5]

Usually the success rate recorded of Ureteroscopy is good around 81-94% according to one study and stone-clearance is also achieved in maximum procedures performed without the need of repeat procedures and with only minimum amount of complications recorded. [6,7]

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted this study on renal a ureteral stones in department of Urology, Sindh Government Lyari General Hospital, and Karachi from January 2015 till

Dec 2018 .We included all patients with stone size less than 2 cm.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients who showed ureter pelvic junction obstruction ,
- Patients with maltreated kidney , horseshoe kidney
- Patients with ectopic kidney and duplex system
- Patients with concomitant stones in ureter or kidney
- Patients who underwent prior ipsilateral urinary tract reconstructive procedures
- Patients with a history of ipsilateral ureteral stricture
- Patients who received prior radiotherapy in abdomen or pelvis
- Patients who had previously undergone stone surgery.

Operative Details:

All the patients suffering from ureteral calculi prospectively underwent ureteroscopic removal. Using ureteroscopy Double-J stent are placed and after the treatment is over, X-ray of the kidney and ureter are checked for documenting stone-clearance.

We obtained the demographics, clinical history and stone size details from the medical record database. However post-operative results and complication details were collected after one month follow-up of only patient who gave consent and we classified results into two categories ; Stone free and clinically insignificant residual fragments (CIRF (≤ 4 mm)).We conducted our analysis and data analysis using SPSS Version 20.

RESULTS:

In our study group, a mean age of 15.29 ± 6.86 years is recorded with a male to female ratio of 59% to 41% where the maximum age documented was 35yr while minimum was 6 year old. (**Table-I**).

Demographics	Variable	Total Population
	Mean Age \pm SD	15.29 \pm 6.86
	Maximum	35 year
	Minimum	6 year
	Male to Female	59% : 41%

Table-I Demographics of Patients

Figure-1 Age Range in ureteral and Renal Calculi Patients

We observed the age bracket of under 11 have the highest number of calculi Patients i.e. 33 out of our total population of 74 while 17-25 being at 23 tallies and 12-14 and 15-17 being the least with only 11 and 4 people falling in this age while 25 to 35 had only 3 patients . **(Figure-1)**

Figure-2 Mean Operation and Hospital time in ureteral and Renal Calculi Patients

The mean operation time observed was 59.03 ± 19.44 mins in Calculi Patients while the mean hospital stay was 1.59 ± 0.826 days. **(Figure-2)**

Figure-3-Details of Stone size and Location Gender wise

The mean stone size recorded in Females is 0.876 cm on left side while Male has mean stone size of 1.05 cm and mean stone size on middle location was 1.225 in Males and 0.985 in Females however in Right side relatively Females had very similar size of Stones as Males; 1.056 cm vs 1.096 cm. Overall the mean stone size is 1.066 cm. **(Figure-3).**We also observed both genders showed maximum number of stones in the middle region.

Figure-4-Post-Operative Complications Gender wise

Patients suffered from stone-migration either upward or downwards around 5% in males or 3% in females. Other complications observed included hematuria, encrustation, dysuria etc. However overall complication rate was higher in males i.e. 14% vs 10% in females. (Figure-5)

Figure-5 Gender-Wise Post-Operative Complication Rate

Patients showed a stone-free rate of **93%** with clinically insignificant residual fragments in only 7% cases (Figure-6).

Figure-6 Stone free and CIRF Rate

DISCUSSION:

Stones in kidney have been identified to cause acute pain however it can be caused due to medications or poor nutrient in diet or less water intake or excessive calcium intake. Although they can flush through the urines depending on their size unless the stone has

moved down in the ureters. Usually males suffer from this pain in their groin area and can sometimes lead to severe situations.

Fluoroscopy is used in numerous investigations however its most frequent use is in diagnosis,

treatment and retrievals of stones in kidney and ureter yet due to its post-operative complications many surgeons prefer using Double J stent or ultrasonography and other flexible techniques.

In our investigations there was no notable difference in mean age of patients and standard deviation in females and males; 15.15 years and 15.38 respectively while *Yuruk et al* studied the mean age to be 10.9 years. ¹². In a local study by *Mohey Ahmed and Colleagues* the mean age observed in the group without fluoroscopy was 29.5 +/- 14.6 years. [14]

According to our data the amount of calculi found is 59% in male and 41% in females. In a similar study 38.8% of renal and ureter calculi patients were Female while 61.2% were males thus showing higher percent in Male. [8]

In our study the mean stone size was 10.6±2.16 mm in patients who underwent ureteroscopy without fluoroscopy and operation time was 59.03 minutes and a similar study shows a mean stone size of 14.7±5 (7–32) mm while the operation time in same study was 72 minutes. [9]

Overall when we evaluated our results we find ureteroscopy without fluoroscopy as a good method as the complication rate was only 12% occurring after the procedure. *Vishwajeet and Colleagues* conducted their study on 41 patients with and without fluoroscopy and their complication rate was slightly lower i.e. 8.75% than our study [10].

Our study showed a stone-free rate of **93%** with clinically insignificant residual fragments in only 7% cases.

In a study by *Deters et al.*[11] they achieved a success rate of 86% stone-free rate slightly lesser than our study. Similarly *Galal et al.* stated that in their investigation on patients under 18 years of age a low complication rate was observed. [13-15] First study on ureteroscopy without fluoroscopy was performed on patients with distal ureteric stones in which authors needed fluoroscope in just 4% of cases without reporting any complication. [16-17]

Although due to lesser researches done on the subject we believe there is a need of more randomized studies for better precision. However, the results of the present study show that ureteroscopy performed without fluoroscopy is safe and feasible.

CONCLUSION:

Thus if we compared the results in female and male patients, we see similar findings with regards to mean age and operation time and hospital stays however the complication rate and resulting stone-free rate show slight variation. Overall the method is safe due to the resulting low complication rate. Although ureteroscopy without fluoroscopy is suggested and used by most surgeons due to radiation exposure, your findings validate it and thus it can be used for most procedure.

REFERENCES:

1. USFDA. Initiative to Reduce Unnecessary Radiation Exposure in Patients. February 2010.
2. Berrington de Gonza'lez A, Darby A. Risk of cancer from diagnostic X-rays: estimates for the UK and 14 other countries. *Lancet* 2004;363: 345–51.
3. USA Food and Drug Administration. Initiative to reduce unnecessary radiation exposure from medical imaging. <http://www.fda.gov/RadiationEmittingProducts/RadiationSafety/RadiationDoseReduction/ucm2007191>.
4. Pearle MS, Calhoun EA, Curhan GC. Urologic Diseases in America project: urolithiasis. *J Urol.* 2005;173:848.
5. Bugher A, Beman M, Holtzman JL, Monga M. Progression of nephrolithiasis: long-term outcomes with observation asymptomatic calculi. *J Endourol.* 2004;18:534–539.
6. Preminger GM, Tiselius HG, Assimos DG, Alken P, Buck C, Gallucci M, et al. 2007 guideline for the management of ureteral calculi. *J Urol.* 2007;178:2418–34.
7. Johnson DB, Pearle MS. Complications of ureteroscopy. *Urol Clin North Am.* 2004;31:157–71.
8. Mustafa Kirac, MD, Giray Ergin, MD, Yusuf Kibar, MD, Burak Ko'pru', MD, and Hasan Biri, MD, "The Efficacy of Ureteroscopy Without Fluoroscopy for Ureteral and Renal Stones in Pediatric Patients", *Journal of Enourology* Feb 2018, 32, (2) :100–105
9. Hacı İbrahim Çimen, Fikret Halis, Hasan Salih Sağlam, and Ahmet Gökçe, "Flouroscopy-free technique is safe and feasible in retrograde intrarenal surgery for renal stones"; *Turk J Urol.* 2017 Sep; 43(3): 309–312.
10. Vishwajeet Singh, Bimalesh Purkait, and Rahul Janak Sinha, "Prospective randomized

- comparison between fluoroscopy-guided ureteroscopy versus ureteroscopy with real-time ultrasonography for the management of ureteral stones”, *Urol Ann.* 2016 Oct-Dec; 8(4): 418–422, doi: 10.4103/0974-7796.192098.
11. Deters LA, Dargosa LM, Herrick BW, Silas A, Pais VM., Jr Ultrasound guided ureteroscopy for the definitive management of ureteral stones: A randomized, controlled trial. *J Urol.* 2014;192:1710–3.
 12. Yuruk E, Tuken M, Gonultas S, et al. Retrograde intrarenal surgery in the management of pediatric cystine stones. *J Pediatr Urol* 2017;13:487.e1–487.e5.
 13. Galal EM, Fath El-Bab TK, Abdelhamid AM. Outcome of ureteroscopy for treatment of pediatric ureteral stones. *J Pediatr Urol* 2013;9:476–478.
 14. Soliman, Tarek & Mohey, Ahmed & Alhefnawy, Mohamed & Mahmoud, Rabea & Ahmed, Shabieb & Noureldin, Yasser. (2017). Fluoroless Ureteroscopy for Definitive Management of Distal Ureteral Calculi: Randomized Controlled Trial. *The Canadian journal of urology.* 25. 10.1016/S1569-9056(18)32234-6.
 15. Kirac M, Ergin G, Kibar Y, Köprü B, Biri H. The efficacy of ureteroscopy without fluoroscopy for ureteral and renal stones in pediatric patients. *Journal of endourology.* 2018 Feb 1;32(2):100-5.
 16. Hu H, Lu Y, He D, Cui L, Zhang J, Zhao Z, Qin B, Wang Y, Lin F, Wang S. Comparison of minimally invasive percutaneous nephrolithotomy and flexible ureteroscopy for the treatment of intermediate proximal ureteral and renal stones in the elderly. *Urolithiasis.* 2016 Oct 1;44(5):427-34.
 17. Çimen Hİ, Halis F, Sağlam HS, Gökçe A. Fluoroscopy-free technique is safe and feasible in retrograde intrarenal surgery for renal stones. *Turkish journal of urology.* 2017 Sep;43(3):309.